

PLANT SYMBOLISM IN THE VICTORIAN AGE OF ENGLISH LITERATURE

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ANNOTATION

This thesis highlighted the Victorian plant symbolism of English literature. During this period, plants reflected a strong sense and a variety of emotions. Today the flowers of the Victorian Era do not have the same meanings they once did.

Key words: symbol, friendship, emotion, Victorian era, traditions, time, culture,

In Victorian culture, flowers were the language of love. Learning the special symbolism of flowers became a popular pastime during the 1800s when each flower was assigned a particular meaning. Feelings that could not be proclaimed publicly could be expressed through flowers. Conservatories were built to house exotic plants while floral designs dominated interior decoration. Nearly all Victorian homes would own at least one of the guide books dedicated to the ‘language of flowers.’ The authors of these guidebooks used visual and verbal analogies, religious and literary sources, folkloric connections, and botanical attributes to derive the various associations for the flowers.

For example bluebells stood for “kindness,” peonies meant “bashfulness,” rosemary was for “remembrance,” tulips represented “passion,” and wallflowers stood for “faithfulness in adversity.” However, plants could also have negative meanings such as aloe, which meant “bitterness,” pomegranate which meant “conceit,” or the rhododendron which meant “danger.” Flowers also varied based on their colors. A white violet meant “innocence” while a purple violet would symbolize that the giver’s “thoughts were occupied with love” about the recipient.

Flower	Latin name	Meaning
Ivy leaf	Hedera helix	Friendship
Rose	Rosa	Love
Passion flower	Passiflora cerulea	Mourning over the death of a loved one
Purple violet	Viola	Thoughts occupied with love
Rosemary	Rosmarinus	Remembrance
Tulips	Tulipia	Passion
Aloe	succotrina	Bitterness

Sending and receiving flowers was a way to show like or dislike toward suitors. If given a rose to declare “devotion” or an apple blossom to show “preference” from a suitor, one might return with a yellow carnation to express “disdain” if it was an undesirable suitor or straw to show a request of “union.” Myrtle was used to symbolize good luck and love in a marriage. In 1858 Queen Victoria’s daughter, also named Victoria, carried a sprig of myrtle taken from a bush planted from a cutting given to the Queen by her mother-in-law. This began a tradition of royal brides including myrtle in their bouquets. Most recently, Prince William’s bride Kate Middleton included sprigs of myrtle from Victoria’s original plant in her own wedding bouquet. In addition, it was fashionable to display the bouquets of meaningful flowers in what are known as ‘Posy Holders.’ These bouquet holders often had rings or pins attached to them so they could be proudly worn and displayed by their owners. Bouquet holders were made out of brass, copper, gold-gilt metal, silver, porcelain, glass, enamel, pearl, ivory, bone and straw and often had intricate engravings and patterning. The Smithsonian Gardens’ Frances Jones Poetker Collection has over 250 of these bouquet holders.

Cedar trees usually denoted strength. Many celebrated courage and

heroism, such as oak leaves, the poplar, black poplar, and the evergreen thorn. The palm tree touted victory over adversity, and the blackthorn tree symbolized the defiance of life's difficulties.

Grief and Darkness

The dark side of things was no less represented. Witch-hazel was often planted at the gates of cemeteries as a symbol of sorrow, though it also traditionally meant that “a spell had been cast.” As for grieving, it was the cypress that meant death, mourning and despair, with the aspen following up with a simple call of lamentation. In kind, the laburnum and the weeping willow portrayed the deep feeling of being forsaken. Yet, hope also grew here, with the pear tree representing comfort. As silent sentinels of time, it makes poetic sense that trees would be part of the language surrounding pain.

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